

Determination of the Dissociation Constant of 1-(5-Chloro-2, 3-dihydroxy-4-pyridylazo)-4-sulphonic Acid and Stability Constants of Its Complexes with $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$, $\text{Ni}(\text{II})$, $\text{Co}(\text{II})$, $\text{Fe}(\text{II})$, $\text{Zn}(\text{II})$, and $\text{Cd}(\text{II})$

J. P. GUPTA, B. S. GARG* and R. P. SINGH

Department of Chemistry, University of Delhi, Delhi-110 007, (India).

Manuscript received 9 November 1977, accepted 8 September 1978.

Dissociation Constant of 1-(5-chloro-2, 3-dihydroxy-4-pyridylazo)-4-sulphonic acid and stability constants of its complexes with $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$, $\text{Ni}(\text{II})$, $\text{Co}(\text{II})$, $\text{Fe}(\text{II})$, $\text{Zn}(\text{II})$ and $\text{Cd}(\text{II})$ have been determined potentiometrically in aqueous medium at different ionic strengths and temperatures. The order of Stability found is: $\text{Cd}(\text{II}) < \text{Zn}(\text{II}) < \text{Co}(\text{II}) < \text{Ni}(\text{II}) < \text{Fe}(\text{II}) < \text{UO}_2(\text{II})$.

Values of ΔG and δH have been calculated.

1-(5-CHLORO-2, 3-dihydroxy-4-pyridylazo)-4-sulphonic acid (CPD-4S) prepared from 5-chloro-2, 3-dihydroxypyridine (CPD) has been used as an analytical reagent for the complexometric determination of $\text{Zn}(\text{II})$, $\text{Cd}(\text{II})$, $\text{Hg}(\text{II})^1$ and $\text{Co}(\text{II})$, $\text{Ni}(\text{II})$, $\text{Cu}(\text{II})^2$. Garg *et al*³ have used the reaction for the formation of CPD-4S as a sensitive test for nitrite through azo-dye formation. The present paper deals with the potentiometric determination of dissociation constant of the CPD-4S and the stability constants of its complexes with some bivalent metals namely $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$, $\text{Ni}(\text{II})$, $\text{Co}(\text{II})$, $\text{Fe}(\text{II})$, $\text{Zn}(\text{II})$ and $\text{Cd}(\text{II})$ in aqueous medium at different ionic strengths and temperatures.

Experimental

Chemicals: 1-(5-Chloro-2,3-dihydroxy-4-pyridylazo)-4-sulphonic acid was prepared by diazotizing sulphonic acid and subsequently coupling the diazotized product with 5-chloro-2,3-dihydroxypyridine. Purity of the ligand was checked by thin layer chromatography and elemental analysis. Elemental analysis data for the ligand are recorded below:

CPD-4S		
	% Calculated	% Found
C	40.00	40.80
H	2.73	2.60
N	12.70	12.90

The IR spectra of CPD-4S recorded in KBr on Perkin-Elmer Infracord, model 137, showed the following results:

Bonds	Frequency cm^{-1}
-N=N-stretching	1600
-S=O stretching	1215
-O-H stretching	3400

*To whom all correspondence should be directed.

The ultraviolet visible absorption spectra of the dye was recorded in double distilled water. The wavelength of maximum absorption is 490 nm and the molar absorptivity is $1.78 \times 10^4 \text{ l mole}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

On the basis of elemental analysis of the dye and the colour reaction which it gives with different metal ions, following tentative structure (I) has been assigned.

Melting point of the purified CPD-4S is high i.e. $>360^\circ$. Solution of the ligand was prepared in double distilled water. All the metal ion solutions were prepared from A. R., B. D. H. samples of the corresponding nitrates or sulphates and were standardized by conventional procedures. Chemically pure sodium perchlorate (Riedel) was used to keep the ionic strengths constant (0.005 M, 0.02 M, 0.1 M and 0.125 M).

A 0.05 M solution of tetramethylammonium hydroxide (TMAH) (E. Merck, A. G., Darmstadt) in doubly distilled water was used as the titrant. It was standardized with a solution of potassium hydrogen phthalate.

An inert atmosphere was maintained by bubbling oxygen-free pre-saturated nitrogen through the solutions during the course of titrations.

Instruments :

A Beckman expandomatic pH-meter, SS-2, with glass electrode (0-14 pH range), was used for pH measurements.

A thermostat, fitted with Beckman thermometer, was used for keeping temperatures constant within $\pm 1^\circ$.

Procedure :

The experimental method of Bjerrum and Calvin as modified by Irving and Rossiti⁴ was used to determine \bar{n} and pL values. The following mixtures (total volume 20 ml, ionic strength adjusted with 2M NaClO₄) were titrated potentiometrically against standard 0.05 M tetramethylammonium hydroxide (TMAH).

(i) 4.0 ml HClO₄ (0.01M)+1.00 ml of nitrate or sulphate (0.01M)

(ii) 4.0 ml HClO₄ (0.01M)+7.5 ml of ligand (M/150)+1.00 ml of nitrate or sulphate (0.01M)

(iii) 4.0 ml HClO₄ (0.01M)+7.5 ml of ligand (M/150)+1.00 ml of metal (0.01M).

In all cases, corrections for changes in volumes which takes place during the course of titrations due to the addition of TMAH, have been made.

Calculations :

In the ligand used for the study, the metal during complexation reaction displaces the hydrogen atom of the -OH group (asterisk marked) and subsequently co-ordinate through the asterisk marked nitrogen atom of the azo group to form 5-membered stable chelate ring. Since only one proton per ligand molecule is liberated on complexation, $Y=1$ in all the cases.

From the titration curves (i) and (ii) of acid

alone and in the presence of ligand, $\bar{n}H$ values of the ligand at various pH values were calculated and the pK_a value of the ligand at different ionic strengths and temperatures were found by plotting $\log \bar{n}H/(1-\bar{n}H)$ vs pH, when a straight line of intercept equal to pK_a and slope equal to 1 was obtained (Figs. 1,2). The values of proton-ligand stability constants are given in Table 1.

Fig. 1. Plots of $\log \left(\frac{\bar{n}H}{1-\bar{n}H} \right)$ vs pH at different ionic strengths (Temp. = 28°)

Fig. 2. Plots of $\log \left(\frac{\bar{n}H}{1-\bar{n}H} \right)$ vs pH at different temperatures (Ionic strength $\approx 0.1M$)

TABLE - 1. STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE BIVALENT METAL CHELATES WITH CPD-4S

Cation → Ionic Strength and temperature.	H ⁺	Cd(II)		Co(II)		Zn(II)		Ni(II)		Fe(II)			UO ₂ (II)						
	log K ₁ ; K ₁	log K ₂ ; K ₂	log β ₂ ; β ₂	log K ₁ ; K ₁	log K ₂ ; K ₂	log β ₂ ; β ₂	log K ₁ ; K ₁	log K ₂ ; K ₂	log β ₂ ; β ₂	log K ₁ ; K ₁	log K ₂ ; K ₂	log β ₂ ; β ₂	log K ₁ ; K ₁	log K ₂ ; K ₂	log β ₂ ; β ₂				
0.005M 28°	5.10	3.22	-	4.01	3.57	7.58	3.85	3.61	7.46	4.57	3.88	8.45	4.68	3.92	3.60	12.20	4.69	3.91	8.60
0.02M 28°	5.06	3.10	-	3.67	-	-	3.60 ¹	3.18	6.78	4.39	3.89	8.28	4.53	3.86	3.42	11.81	4.65	3.89	8.54
0.1M 28°	4.92	3.07	-	3.57	-	-	3.53	-	-	4.22	3.88	8.10	4.29	3.78	3.52	11.59	4.62	3.82	8.44
0.125M 28°	4.88	3.01	-	3.46	-	-	3.34	-	-	3.97	3.67	7.64	4.15	3.64	3.50	11.29	4.53	3.75	8.28
0.1M 40°	4.84	3.15	-	3.47	-	-	3.50	-	-	4.15	3.75	7.90	4.11	3.68	3.54	11.39	4.49	3.61	8.10
0.1M 50°	4.77	-	-	3.45	-	-	3.44	-	-	4.10	3.60	7.70	4.03	3.78	3.29	11.10	4.42	3.48	7.90

From the titration curves of solutions (ii) and (iii), \bar{n} values of the metal complexes were determined at various pH values. From a knowledge of practical pK_a value and \bar{n} value at a particular pH, the corresponding value of pL was then calculated. The \bar{n} values are plotted against the corresponding pL value to give the formation curve of the metal complex equilibria. One such plot at 0.1M ionic strength and 28° is shown in Fig. 3. The values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were calculated by using the "Correction term method" of Irving and Rossotti⁵. In the cases where the formation curves show steep rise in \bar{n} without significant change in pL , only $\log K_1$ values were obtained by the Bjerrum's half \bar{n} method⁶. $\log K_2$ value in case of iron was obtained by making use of the general equation given below and the value was refined by recalculating K_1 , K_2 and K_3 till constancy in K_3 was obtained.

Fig. 3. Formation curves of bivalent metal complexes with CPD-4S in water at I.S.=0.1M=28 temperature.

$$K_3 = \frac{\bar{n} + (\bar{n} - 1)K_1[L] + (\bar{n} - 2)K_1K_2[L]^2}{(3 - \bar{n})K_1K_2[L]^3}$$

Results and Discussion

From the results (Table 1) it is seen that pK_a value of the ligand decreases with increase in ionic strength and temperature. The pK_a value of the ligand at zero ionic strength obtained by extrapolation is 5.11. The comparatively lower pK_a value of CPD-4S as compared to that of 5-chloro-2,3-dihydroxypyridine (CPD) is explained by the fact that azo-group in CPD-4S has electron withdrawing character and as a result of it negative charge density on oxygen of the asterisk marked hydroxyl group is reduced and proton is liberated comparatively easily.

The order of stability of bivalent metal complexes is as follows :

Except for the ferrous complex, this sequence is in agreement with the Irving-William order⁸. An abnormally high stability of Fe(II) complexes has been observed in many cases, particularly with aromatic ligands *i.e.* riboflavin⁹, folic acid⁹, *o*-phenanthroline¹⁰ etc. It has been attributed to the resonance stabilization energy of Fe(II) complexes upon co-ordination with a ligand having an aromatic ring system¹⁰. Oxidation of Fe(II) to Fe(III) could not have occurred during the titrations which were performed in inert (nitrogen) atmosphere.

Formation curve for copper could not be drawn because the pH drops too sharply by release of hydrogen ions on chelation. This type of behaviour has also been reported for nickel(II) with 4-(2-pyridylazo)-resorcinol¹¹ and 1-(2-pyridylazo)-2-phenanthroline¹². The stability of metal chelates has been found to decrease with increase in temperature and ionic strength (Table 1), which is in accordance with expectations.

From the $\log K_1$ values of the complexes at different temperatures, the δH values have been calculated using Van't Hoff equation. The values are given in Table 2.

TABLE-2. CALCULATIONS OF δH VALUES FOR COMPLEXES OF CPD-4S ($\mu \approx 0.1$ M, TEMP. = 301°K)

Cations →	Fe(II)	Co(II)	Ni(II)	Zn(II)
$\log K_1$	4.29	3.57	4.22	3.53
ΔG° Cal/mol	5.94	4.92	5.81	4.84
ΔH_c	4	2	3	2
ΔH_H	20	43	62	47
H_L	30	45	65	49
$(n-5)/5 E_f$	10	20	30	-
H	20	25	35	-

ΔG -Free energy change = 2.303 RT log K (where R, T and K have the usual significance)

ΔH_c -Change in heat content for the formation of the complex in solution (Obtained by Van't Hoff equation).

ΔH_H -Heat of hydration of metal ion.

ΔH_L -Heat of complexation referred to metal ion in gaseous and ligand in solution state.

n-Number of electrons in 3d orbital.

E_f -Lattice energy difference for $Zn(II)$ and $Mn(II)$ complexes.

H-Thermodynamic stabilization energy.

The values of δH observed for the Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes are also of the same order as for other ligands co-ordinating through one nitrogen atom. This indicates that the metal ions are bonded through one nitrogen and one oxygen atom to the ligand molecule.

Some of the complexes of CPD-4S with different metals were isolated. I. R. spectra of these complexes showed that $-N=N-$ stretching frequency shifts to a lower value. This confirms that the metal form complex with the ligand through nitrogen atom of the azo group and hence $-OH$ ortho to the azo group will take part in chelate formation.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (J. P. G.) is thankful to U. G. C., New Delhi (India) for providing financial assistance.

References

1. Y. L. MEHTA, B. S. GARG and MOHAN KATYAL, *Analytica Chim. Acta.*, 1976, 86, 323.
2. J. P. GUPTA, Y. L. MEHTA, B. S. GARG and R. P. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, 14A, 256.
3. B. S. GARG, Y. L. MEHTA and MOHAN KATYAL, *Talanta*, 1976, 23, 71.
4. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
5. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397.
6. J. BJERRUM, "Metal Amine Formation in Aqueous Solution", P. Haase and Son, Copenhagen, 1941.
7. VEENA KUSHWAHA, Ph.D. Thesis, "Analytical Applications of Some Hydroxypyridines", University of Delhi, Delhi, 1973, 51.
8. H. IRVING and R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3192.
9. A. ALBERT, *Biochem. J.*, 1953, 54, 646.
10. H. IRVING and R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3206.
11. W. J. GEARY, G. NICKLESS and F. H. POLLARD, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1962, 27, 71
12. A. K. RISHI, Ph.D. THESIS, "Metal Chelates of 1-(2-pyridylazo)-2-phenanthrol", University of Delhi, Delhi, 1972, 46.